

GES4SEAS POLICY BRIEF #5

HEALTHY OCEANS FOR HEALTHY SOCIETIES

How can this Policy Brief support you?

This Policy Brief supports all marine practitioners, those who devise and apply policy and those affected by the policies, who need to show that the seas should remain healthy. This must be both for nature, by supporting the ecological structure and functioning, and for humans who can continue obtaining goods and benefits from the seas. It gives existing and new approaches and methods which focus on healthy oceans. It furthermore emphasises how practitioners should define natural and societal health and focus on the metrics available for determining whether or not management reaches these as a goal.

Key Messages

A healthy coastal and marine environment should meet the overall vision to be clean, healthy, safe, productive, biologically diverse and managed to meet the long-term needs of people and nature.

A healthy ocean is measured and assessed by indicators underpinned by monitoring and showing a natural structure and functioning despite human activities.

A healthy ocean should be resistant to human pressures or, at least where those pressures exceed the assimilative and carrying capacities, then the ocean should be resilient in regaining its original status if pressures are removed.

If the pressures cause a tipping point to be exceeded, then management should ensure the new system also fulfils healthy criteria for nature and society.

It is assumed that an area meeting Good Environmental Status (GES) under the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) is in a healthy state or at least in a fit-for-purpose condition for nature and people.

It is also assumed that healthy oceans satisfy the sustainability goals.

Marine management should maintain and protect ecological structure and functioning while at the same time allowing the system to produce ecosystem services from which we derive societal goods and benefits.

Narrative of the problem, with GES4SEAS examples

A healthy ocean underpins both ecological integrity and societal well-being. It should maintain physico-chemical processes and their stability which are required to support ecological structure and functioning. Then it should help to fulfil basic human needs as shown by Maslow's Hierarchy for welfare, culture, enjoyment, food and the regulation of our environment

by healthy oceans (Figure 1). The health of the seas is shown by the cascade, a so-called logic chain, of the ecology maintaining the natural capital which creates ecosystems services. From these we carry out marine activities to gather societal goods and benefits after inputting human built and social capital (see Figure 2). This requires inputting time, financial investment, energy, skills and the ability to be sentient to satisfy basic human needs.

Figure 1. Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs in relation to ocean health

Figure 2. The marine environmental cascade from the natural domain to the human domain (the natural domain valued ecologically; the human domain valued in monetary and non-monetary terms)

Knowing and monitoring the changes in the natural and societal condition then requires management responses using, for example, Programmes of Measures as embedded in many environmental legal instruments and Directives (e.g. MSFD). Implementing these directives indicate the healthy status of ecological components as shown by fulfilling indicators. The target conditions of these indicators show the ability to maintain the cascade across the natural and human domains with a healthy, resistant and resilient ocean. The indicators thus reveal whether ecosystems can continue providing essential services and benefits for humans despite the activities and their pressures.

Natural ecological health can be assessed by ecological valuation which does not include human aspects in such an estimation. In contrast, monetary and non-monetary values can be used as proxies for the health of oceans for human uses, goods and benefits.

The Crete Declaration, in which GES4SEAS has participated, reinforces the need to address hazards and risks affecting both marine ecosystems and human communities to advance the One Health approach. Effective ocean management and governance to maintain and assure natural and human health and well-being must integrate ecology with law, administration, technology, economics, politics, societal demands, culture, ethics, stakeholder participation and communication. Integrated marine management should be centred on risk assessment and risk management showing the causes and consequences of change, the prevention and mitigation of those changes and the restoration of degraded systems.

Policy implications

European Directives

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive (the Programme of Measures should consider the health implications of not achieving GES);
- Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD, the CEA analysis should help to identify areas at risk and responsible pressures and activities, so they can be adequately managed);
- Natura 2000 Directives (to maintain natural health as Favourable Conservation Status);
- Nature Restoration Regulation (identifying risk areas/habitats/ species is key to determine fit-for-purpose restoration measures that secure ecosystem services and their goods and benefits);
- Water Framework Directive (catchment health as ecological and chemical status);
- All other environmental regulations.

Other Policy / International Objectives

- Regional Seas Conventions;
- UN Convention on Law of the Sea;
- Convention on Biological Diversity;
- UN Convention on Climate Change;
- European Environment Agency (EEA, including Marine Messages 3);
- All other environmental agreements.

Sustainable Development Goals

The GES4SEAS tools link directly or indirectly to many of the SDG:

Beyond the State-of-the-Art

For policy-makers, assessing ocean health, in the framework of the MSFD requires understanding the links between human activities, pressures and environmental status. GES4SEAS has developed tools that increase understanding of the human-ocean interactions (Pressure2Eco), to determine risk areas and responsible activities and pressures (Tikta-CEA), to assess the actual environmental status (Tikta-NEAT), and the link with the provision of ecosystem services and goods and benefits (SCAIRM). The GES4SEAS work on Cumulative Effects Assessment aims to stop areas passing the assimilative capacity into unhealthy systems. This suite of tools supports the definition of Programme of Measures that can deliver healthy oceans for healthy societies.

Environmental status assessment ensures that policy decisions also reflect the intrinsic health of marine systems,

as GES4SEAS has demonstrated and published, using the MSFD assessments from all Member States. As a novel analysis, GES4SEAS collated data regarding the attaining of GES by EU Member States. Similarly, the EU Ocean Pact, informed by GES4SEAS research, proposes the development and application of a European Ocean Health Index. Such an Index could be developed from the Baltic Sea Health Index, the original Ocean Health Index and the EEA MESH index. The European 'Marine Ecosystem Health Index', developed during the EEA Marine Messages 3 process (in draft 2026), is an indicator-based framework for assessing ecosystem health. These two state-of-the-art data sets, show that the marine waters of EU Member States are not yet fulfilling the vision indicated at the start of the Policy Brief.

Key Facts

Activity managers and regulators have a duty to ensure that the seas are maintained in a healthy state and sustainable despite the activities.

The health of the ocean should relate to both the natural and human status and features.

The protection of the natural system at the expense of human benefits will mean that the blue economy is not fulfilled.

The delivery of human benefits at the expense of the natural system will mean that biodiversity suffers and international nature conservation obligations are not fulfilled.

Balancing human health (as the wise use of the ocean space) and natural health (achieving GES) respectively require the integration of the MSPD and MSFD.

Achieving this balance is crucial for, and does not compromise the uses of the seas by, present and future generations.

Authors:

Elliott, M., Borja, A., Andersen, J., Franco, A., Papadopoulou, N., Smith, C., Uyarra, M.C.

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19201997

References from GES4SEAS

For GES4SEAS resources and references click this [link](#) or scan this QR code.

For references from outside GES4SEAS see:

Blenckner, T., et al., 2021. *People and Nature* 3:359–375; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10178>.

EC The European Ocean Pact COM/2025/281 final <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025DC0281>.

Elliott, M., 2023. *Mar. Poll. Bull.*, 193: 115177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115177>.

EEA, 2026, *Marine Messages III*, European Topic Centre for Biodiversity and Ecosystems.

Halpern, B., et al., 2012, *Nature*, 488: 615; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11397>.

For additional resources from the GES4SEAS project, visit the webpages: <https://www.ges4seas.eu> and <https://www.ges4seas.eu/toolbox/>

For more information about these and other GES4SEAS publications, scan the QR code

